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Education

- 2023 Doctor of Philosophy, Second Temple Judaism/Dead Sea Scrolls
Department of Theology and Religion, University of Birmingham, UK
Professor Charlotte Hempel, Ph.D., Supervisor
Dissertation, *Out of the Wilderness: Studies on the Qumran War Tradition*
Examiners: Professor Hugh Houghton, Ph.D., University of Birmingham, UK and Ariel Feldman, Ph.D., Brite Divinity School, Texas Christian University
- 2011 Master of Arts in Religion, Biblical Studies
Azusa Pacific Graduate School of Theology, Azusa, CA
Karen Strand Winslow, Ph.D., Advisor
Thesis, *Textual Tradition and Transmission within Enochic and Qumran Literature: A Comparative Study of The Book of Watchers and Peshar Habakkuk*
- 1989 Bachelor of Arts, Religion
Azusa Pacific University, Azusa, CA
Magna Cum Laude

Academic Positions

- | | | |
|--------------|-----------------------------|--|
| 2018–present | Senior Adjunct Professor | Azusa Pacific University/Azusa Pacific Seminary, Azusa, CA |
| 2017–2018 | Assistant Professor | Azusa Pacific University, Azusa, CA (One-year contract) |
| 2013–2017 | Adjunct Professor | Azusa Pacific University, Azusa, CA |
| 2012–2019 | Adjunct Professor | Hope International University, Fullerton, CA |
| 2012–2013 | Teaching Assistant/Lecturer | Azusa Pacific Graduate School of Theology, Azusa, CA |

Professional Positions

- 2024–present Board Member, Second Temple Early Career Academy (STECA)
- 2023–present Associate Editor, *Reviews of the Enoch Seminar* (RES)
- 2020 Publication Assistant to Charlotte Hempel, University of Birmingham, UK
- 2018–2020 Steering Committee and Founding Member, Second Temple Early Career Academy (STECA), University of Birmingham, UK

Awards, Scholarships, and Grants

- 2019, 2018 College of Arts and Law Graduate School Research Support Fund, University of Birmingham, UK
- 1989 Religion Student of the Year, Azusa Pacific University

Publications

Monographs

Michael DeVries, *Out of the Wilderness: Studies in the Qumran War Tradition* (Brill: Leiden). Passed peer review and is currently being revised for publication in the *Studies on the Texts of the Judean Desert* Series.

Edited Volumes

- Charlotte Hempel and Michael DeVries, eds., *Ezra and the Dead Sea Scrolls: New Perspectives*, EJL (Atlanta: SBL Press, 2026).
- George J. Brooke and Charlotte Hempel, eds., With the Assistance of Michael DeVries and Drew Longacre, *T&T Clark Companion to the Dead Sea Scrolls* (London: Bloomsbury T&T Clark, 2019).

Chapters in Edited Volumes

- “Remnant and Identity Formation in Ezra-Nehemiah and the *Damascus Document*,” in *Ezra and the Dead Sea Scrolls: New Perspectives*, eds. Charlotte Hempel and Michael DeVries, EJL (Atlanta: SBL Press, 2026).
- “Eschatological Violence in the Dead Sea Scrolls,” in *The Bible and Violence*, eds. Chris Greenough, Johnathan Jodamus, Mmapula Diana Kebaneilwe, and Johanna Stiebert (London: Bloomsbury T&T Clark, 2026).
- “*Ḥerem* (חֲרָם) and *Hāmās* (חֲמָס): A Focused Study,” in *The Bible and Violence*, eds. Chris Greenough, Johnathan Jodamus, Mmapula Diana Kebaneilwe, and Johanna Stiebert (London: Bloomsbury T&T Clark, 2026).
- “Purity and Cult in the Qumran War Texts: A Reconsideration,” in *Purity in Ancient Judaism: Texts, Contexts, and Concepts*, eds. Lutz Doering, Jörg Frey, and Laura von Bartenwerffer, WUNT 1/528 (Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2025), 239–54. (<https://doi.org/10.1628/978-3-16-164165-7>)
- “Ritual Studies and the Dead Sea Scrolls: A Review,” (co-authored with Jutta Jokiranta) in *The Dead Sea Scrolls in Ancient Media Culture*, eds. Travis B. Williams, Chris Keith, and Loren T. Stuckenbruck, STDJ 144 (Leiden: Brill, 2023), 156–96. (https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004537804_006)

Encyclopedia and Dictionary Entries

- “Kittim,” in *Brill’s Online Encyclopedia of the Dead Sea Scrolls: A New Research Tool for the Study of the Dead Sea Scrolls*, eds. James C. VanderKam, Lawrence H. Schiffman, and Sidnie White Crawford (Online, forthcoming).
- “Mastemah,” in *Brill’s Online Encyclopedia of the Dead Sea Scrolls: A New Research Tool for the Study of the Dead Sea Scrolls*, eds. James C. VanderKam, Lawrence H. Schiffman, and Sidnie White Crawford (Online, forthcoming).
- “Rules and Rule Scrolls in the Dead Sea Scrolls,” (co-authored with Charlotte Hempel) in *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Religion*, Oxford University Press (Online, https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780199340378.013.ORE_REL-01064.R1)

Book Reviews

- Books reviewed for *Bibliotheca Orientalis*, *Catholic Biblical Quarterly*, *Dead Sea Discoveries*, *The Expository Times*, *Journal of Jewish Studies*, *Journal of Theological Studies*, *Reading Religion* (AAR), *Review of Biblical Literature* (SBL), and *Revue de Qumrân*.
- Lorenzo DiTommaso and Matthew Goff, eds., *Reimagining Apocalypticism: Apocalyptic Literature in the Dead Sea Scrolls and Related Writings*, EJL 57 (Atlanta: SBL Press, 2023). Reviewed for *Review of Biblical Literature*, forthcoming.
- Étienne Nodet, *A Gate to Heaven: Essenes, Qumran: Origins and Heirs*, Jewish and Christian Texts in Context and Related Studies 37 (London: Bloomsbury T&T Clark, 2023). Reviewed for *Reading Religion*, forthcoming.
- Pieter B. Hartog and Andrew B. Perrin, eds., *The Dead Sea Scrolls in the Context of Hellenistic Judea: Proceedings of the Tenth Meeting of the International Organization for Qumran Studies (Aberdeen, 5–8 August, 2019)*, STDJ 142 (Leiden: Brill, 2023). Reviewed for *Review of Biblical Literature*, forthcoming.
- Anthony Giambrone, OP, *The Bible and the Priesthood: Priestly Participation in the Sacrifice for Sins* (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2022). Reviewed for *Catholic Biblical Quarterly*, forthcoming.
- Hanna Vanonen, *War Traditions from the Qumran Caves: Re-Thinking Textual Stability and Fluidity in the War Text Manuscripts*, STDJ 139 (Leiden: Brill, 2022). Reviewed for *Revue de Qumrân*, forthcoming.
- Jörg Frey, with Jacob Cerone, *Qumran and Christian Origins* (Waco, TX: Baylor University Press, 2022). Reviewed for *Reading Religion*, posted on 29 July 2024. (<https://readingreligion.org/9781481317641/>)

- Timothy H. Lim, *The Earliest Commentary on the Prophecy of Habakkuk*, OCDSS (New York: Oxford University Press, 2020). Reviewed for *Journal of Jewish Studies*, 75.1 (Spring 2024), 188–90. (<https://doi.org/10.3828/jjs.2024.75.1.188>)
- Christopher Rowland, “*By an Immediate Revelation*”: *Studies in Apocalypticism, Its Origins and Effects*, WUNT 473 (Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2022). Reviewed for *Reading Religion*, posted on 29 August 2023. (<https://readingreligion.org/9783161597862/>)
- David G. Firth, *Joshua: Evangelical Biblical Theology Commentary* (Bellingham, WA: Lexham Academic, 2021). Reviewed for *Catholic Biblical Quarterly*, 85.1 (2023): 135–37.
- Annette Yoshiko Reed, *Demons, Angels, and Writing in Ancient Judaism* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020). Reviewed for *Reading Religion*, posted on 23 January 2023. (<https://readingreligion.org/9781108776103/>)
- Jessica M. Keady, *Vulnerability and Valour: A Gendered Analysis of Everyday Life in the Dead Sea Scrolls Community*, LSTS 91 (London: Bloomsbury T&T Clark, 2017). Reviewed for *Review of Biblical Literature*, posted on 13 January 2023. (https://www.sblcentral.org/API/Reviews/11649_72344.pdf)
- Carmen Palmer, *Converts in the Dead Sea Scrolls: The Gēr and Mutable Ethnicity*, STDJ 126 (Leiden: Brill, 2018). Reviewed for *Reading Religion*, posted on 18 May 2022. (<https://readingreligion.org/9789004378179/>)
- Jesper Høgenhaven, *The Cave 3 Copper Scroll: A Symbolic Journey*, STDJ 132 (Leiden: Brill, 2020). Reviewed for *Bibliotheca Orientalis*, 78 5/6 (2022): 729–32.
- Henryk Drawnel, ed., *Sacred Texts and Disparate Interpretations: Qumran Manuscripts Seventy Years Later; Proceedings of the International Conference Held at the John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin, 24-26 October 2017*, STDJ 133 (Leiden: Brill, 2020). Reviewed for *Catholic Biblical Quarterly* 84.1 (2022): 155–57.
- Amsalu Tefera and Loren T. Stuckenbruck, eds., *Representations of Angelic Beings in Early Judaism and in Christian Tradition*, WUNT 2/544 (Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2021). Reviewed for *Reading Religion*, posted on 20 October 2021. (<https://readingreligion.org/9783161597602/>)
- George J. Brooke and Charlotte Hempel, eds., *T&T Clark Companion to the Dead Sea Scrolls* (London/New York: Bloomsbury T&T Clark, 2018). Reviewed for *Journal of Jewish Studies* 71.1 (Spring 2020): 193–95. (<https://doi.org/10.18647/3446/jjs-2020>)
- Pieter B. Hartog, Alison Schofield, and Samuel I. Thomas, eds., *The Dead Sea Scrolls and the Study of the Humanities: Method, Theory, Meaning: Proceedings of the Eighth Meeting of the International Organization for Qumran Studies (Munich, 4–7 August, 2013)*, STDJ 125 (Leiden: Brill, 2018). Reviewed for *Journal of Theological Studies* 71 (2020): 311–13. (<https://doi.org/10.1093/jts/flaa018>)
- Andrew B. Perrin, Kyung S. Baek, and Daniel K. Falk, eds., *Reading the Bible in Ancient Traditions and Modern Editions: Studies in Memory of Peter W. Flint*, EJL 47 (Atlanta: SBL Press, 2017). Reviewed for *Dead Sea Discoveries* 26.2 (2019): 253–55. (<https://doi.org/10.1163/15685179-12341510>)
- Daniel Stökl Ben Ezra, *Qumran: Die Texte vom Toten Meer und das antike Judentum*, Jüdische Studien 4681 (Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2016). Reviewed for *Journal of Jewish Studies* 70.1 (Spring 2019): 196–98. (<https://doi.org/10.18647/3406/jjs-2019>)
- Gwynned de Looijer, *The Qumran Paradigm: A Critical Evaluation of Some Foundational Hypotheses in the Construction of the Qumran Sect*, EJL 43 (Atlanta: SBL Press, 2015). Reviewed for *The Expository Times* 129.4 (2018): 180–81. (<https://doi.org/10.1177/0014524617726024>)
- Kipp Davis, Dorothy M. Peters, Kyung S. Baek, and Peter W. Flint, eds., *The War Scroll, Violence, War and Peace in the Dead Sea Scrolls and Related Literature: Essays in Honour of Martin G. Abegg on the Occasion of His 65th Birthday*, STDJ 115 (Leiden: Brill, 2015). Reviewed for *Ancient Jew Review*, posted on 15 February 2017. (<https://www.ancientjewreview.com/read/2017/2/15/war-violence-and-peace-in-the-dead-sea-scrolls>)

Papers and Presentations

“How are Ritual and Anxiety Connected from a Cognitive Perspective?” Co-presentation with Jutta Jokiranta in Anxiety and Ritual, Joint Session of the Qumran and Hellenistic Judaism Sections, Society of Biblical Literature Annual Meeting, Boston, MA, 23 November 2025.

- “Shared Meals in the Qumran Movement: A Cognitive Assessment,” Joint Session of Qumran and the Dead Sea Scrolls Section (SBL) and the Dead Sea Scrolls (EABS): Rituals of Group Belonging and Cognitive Science, Society of Biblical Literature/European Association of Biblical Studies International Meeting, Uppsala, Sweden, 26 June 2025.
- “Ritual, Cognition, and the Qumran Movement,” Second Temple Early Career Academy (STECA) Virtual Conference, 23 May 2025
- “Remnant and Exile in Ezra-Nehemiah and the Damascus Document,” Chronicles-Ezra-Nehemiah Section, Society of Biblical Literature Annual Meeting, San Diego, CA, 25 November 2024.
- “Priestly Exhortatory Speech Traditions in the Qumran War Tradition,” Fighting Talk – Motivating Violence in Ancient Judaism Conference, University of Agder, Kristiansand, Norway, 5 June 2024.
- “The History of the Azusa Pacific University Fragments: A Cautionary Tale,” The Lying Pen Dead Sea Scrolls Symposium, University of Agder, Kristiansand, Norway, 4 June 2024.
- “Provenance and Dead Sea Scrolls Research,” The Dead Sea Scrolls as a Scholarly Phenomenon Conference, University of Agder, Kristiansand, Norway, 13 December 2022.
- “Wilderness and Warfare: The Wilderness Motif in the Qumran War Tradition,” Department of Theology and Religion, Postgraduate Research Forum, University of Birmingham, Birmingham, UK, 26 May 2022.
- “Purity and Defilement in the Qumran War Tradition,” European Association of Biblical Studies 2021 Graduate Symposium, Mainz, Germany, 27 May 2021.
- “Ritual as Rhetoric: The Textualization of Ritual in the Qumran War Scroll,” Categories and Boundaries in Second Temple Jewish Literature Conference 2021, University of Birmingham, Birmingham, UK, 5 March 2021.
- “Purity and Defilement in Qumran Eschatological Imagination,” The European Association of Biblical Studies 2020 Graduate Symposium, Jerusalem, Israel. (Cancelled due to COVID-19)
- “Purity and Cult in the Qumran War Texts,” Department of Theology and Religion, Biblical Studies Seminar, University of Birmingham, Birmingham, UK, 15 January 2020.
- “The Concept of *Herem* in Ezra and the Dead Sea Scrolls,” Ezra-Nehemiah and the Dead Sea Scrolls Conference, University of Birmingham, Birmingham, UK, 8 December 2019.
- “Purity and Cult in the Qumran War Texts: A Reconsideration,” Purity in Ancient Judaism and Early Christianity: 10th Schwerte Qumran Meeting, Katholische Akademie Schwerte, Schwerte, Germany, 11 February 2019.
- “Liturgical and Ritualized Warfare in the War Scroll and Related War Texts,” University of Birmingham Department of Theology and Religion Postgraduate Research Showcase, Society of Biblical Literature Annual Meeting, Boston, MA, 19 November 2017.
- “The Priesthood in Times of War: Sacerdotal and Militaristic Functions,” Western Jewish Studies Association 2017 Annual Conference, Claremont McKenna College, Claremont, CA, 26 March 2017.
- “Cult and Warfare: The Role of the Priesthood in 1QM,” Society of Biblical Literature Pacific Coast Regional Meeting, Hope International University, Fullerton, CA, 12 March 2017.
- “When You Are Encamped Against Your Enemies: Purity Rules for the War Camp in Deuteronomy and 1QM,” Society of Biblical Literature Pacific Coast Regional Meeting, Claremont Graduate University, Claremont, CA, 14 March 2016.

Invited Presentations

- “The Temple Scroll,” SASA Virtual Seminar: The Ancient Library of the Dead Sea Scrolls, 23 July 2020.
(<https://www.saveancientstudies.org>)
- “Text and Transmission: The ‘Bible’ at Qumran,” GSPH 506 Spiritual Concept Analysis in Health Care, Azusa Pacific University, Azusa, CA, 9 July 2020.
- “The ‘Biblical’ Text at Qumran,” GSPH 506 Spiritual Concept Analysis in Health Care, Azusa Pacific University, Azusa, CA, 28 May 2020.
- “The Community of Qumran and Apocalyptic,” UBBL 472 Biblical Apocalyptic, Azusa Pacific University, Azusa, CA, 5 February 2020.

- “Material Culture and Scribal Practice at Qumran,” GBBL 651 Scripture and Canon, Azusa Pacific Seminary, Azusa, CA, 21 February 2018.
- “Qumran Cave 1 Texts,” GBBL 611 The Dead Sea Scrolls and the Biblical World, Azusa Pacific Seminary, Los Angeles, CA, 12 July 2016.
- “The Intertextual Use of Deuteronomy in 1QM,” GBBL 501 Torah and Prophets, Azusa Pacific Seminary, Azusa, CA, 18 February 2016.
- “The Rise of Jewish Apocalyptic Literature,” GBBL 631 Kingdom of God, Azusa Pacific Graduate School of Theology, San Diego, CA, 8 April 2013.
- “The Role of Memory in the Book of Deuteronomy,” GBBL 521 People of God, Azusa Pacific Graduate School of Theology, Azusa CA, 15 November 2012.
- “‘Making the Hands Unclean’: The Storing Away of Scrolls,” GBBL 611 Scripture and Canon, Azusa Pacific Graduate School of Theology, Azusa, CA, 24 March 2011.
- “The Book of Daniel and Apocalyptic Literature,” GBBL 631 Community of God, Azusa Pacific Graduate School of Theology, Azusa, CA, 3 December 2009.

Conference Organization and Participation

- Planning Committee for Second Temple Early Career Academy (STECA) Virtual Conference, 23 March 2025. (The program featured researchers from institutions in Brazil, Denmark, Singapore, the United Kingdom, and the United States.)
- Chair, “Reception and Interpretation of the Dead Sea Scrolls and Their Scholarship” Session at “The Dead Sea Scrolls as a Scholarly Phenomenon” Conference at University of Agder, Kristiansand, Norway, 14 December 2022.
- Planning Committee for “The Dead Sea Scrolls as a Scholarly Phenomenon Conference” at University of Agder, Kristiansand, Norway, 12–14 December 2022. (Conference was granted € 13,500 from the Research Council of Norway and the University of Agder. The program featured researchers from institutions in Belgium, Brazil, Germany, Israel, Norway, Sweden, the United Kingdom, and the United States.)
- Coordinator, University of Birmingham Department of Theology and Religion Postgraduate Research Showcase, Society of Biblical Literature Annual Meeting, Boston, MA, 19 November 2017.

Courses and Instruction

Azusa Pacific Seminary, Department of Biblical and Theological Studies

- GBBL 611 The Dead Sea Scrolls and the Biblical Text
- GBBL 570 Directed Research: Eschatology, Messianism, and the Qumran Movement
- GBBL 540 Hebrew II
- GBBL 530 Hebrew I
- PRBL 230 Luke/Acts

Azusa Pacific University, Department of Biblical and Religious Studies

- HEBB 455 Hebrew Readings: Qumran Hebrew
- HEBB 201 Elementary Hebrew II
- HEBB 200 Elementary Hebrew I
- SOT 150 Understanding the Old Testament: Creation, Covenant, Exile, Restoration
- UBBL 497 Sectarianism and the Qumran Movement
- UBBL 472 Biblical Apocalyptic
- UBBL 420 The Dead Sea Scrolls and the Biblical World
- UBBL 311 Israelite Prophets
- UBBL 310 The Rise of the King: I and II Samuel
- UBBL 230 Luke/Acts
- UBBL 100 Introduction to Biblical Literature: Exodus/Deuteronomy

Hope International University, Department of Biblical Studies

BIB3300 Pentateuch

BIB2330/5330 Psalms

BIB1325/5013 History and Literature of Ancient Israel

Azusa Pacific Graduate School of Theology

GBBL 531 Kingdom of God (Teaching Assistant and Lecturer)

GBBL 521 People of God (Teaching Assistant and Lecturer)

Public Engagement

The Breakfast Show/Voice of Islam Radio UK, Guest on “The Breakfast Show” discussing the origins and ancient textual traditions concerning Hanukkah, 2 December 2021.

Ancient Afterlives, “Dead Sea Scrolls in the Modern Era: Provenance and Forgery,” Interview with Ingrid Breilid Gimse for *Ancient Afterlives* podcast, Episode 9, posted on 21 October (Part 1) and 4 November (Part 2) 2021.

Ancient Afterlives, “War Scroll and Trauma,” Coffee Chat with Simeon Whiting for *Ancient Afterlives* podcast discussing the intersection of our respective doctoral research, Episode 8, posted on 7 October 2021.

Digital Hammurabi, Guest on the *Digital Hammurabi* podcast discussing Dead Sea Scrolls research and the *Ancient Afterlives* podcast, 11 September 2021. (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F422RbC4eQ>)

“The Shema as *Halakhah*: A Way of Living,” Common Day of Learning, Azusa Pacific University, Azusa, CA, 23 February 2016.

“The Concept of the Afterlife in Jewish Thought,” Saddleback College, Mission Viejo, CA, 4 November 2015.

Editorial Assistance

Charlotte Hempel, *The Community Rules from Qumran: A Commentary*, TSAJ 183 (Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2020). Preparation of indices.

George J. Brooke and Charlotte Hempel, eds., With the assistance of Michael DeVries and Drew Longacre, *T&T Clark Companion to the Dead Sea Scrolls* (London/New York: Bloomsbury T&T Clark, 2019). Editorial and preparation of indices.

Research Supervision and Examination Committees

Research Supervision

Gregory Morton (M.A., 2020) on messianism in the Qumran corpus.

Examination Committees

Gregory Morton, “Messianism of the Dead Sea Scrolls: A Reassessment,” M.A. thesis successfully defended on 10 December 2020, Azusa Pacific Seminary, conducted via Zoom.

Professional Memberships

British and Irish Association for Jewish Studies

Catholic Biblical Association

Enoch Seminar

European Association of Biblical Studies

International Association for the Cognitive and Evolutionary Sciences of Religion

Society of Biblical Literature

Language Proficiencies

Ancient: Biblical Hebrew, Qumran Hebrew, Aramaic, Greek (Koine)

Modern: French, German, Hebrew

References

Professor Charlotte Hempel, Ph.D.

Professor of Hebrew Bible and Second Temple Judaism
Department of Theology and Religion
Head of the School of Philosophy, Theology and Religion
University of Birmingham
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Professor George J. Brooke, Ph.D., D.D., D.Sc.Rel. (hc)

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Professor Jutta Jokiranta, Ph.D.

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